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Current trends in the field of International English language tests: factors contributing to the computerization of exams in Uzbekistan

The programme

Programme

- British Council Overview
- IELTS: Steps toward computerisation
- Current stance of IELTS
- Delivery modes of IELTS
- Integration of Video Call Speaking in IELTS
- The IELTS test on computer (advantages and peculiarities)
- One Skill Retake
- Links to resources (Preparation Materials)

Steps toward Computerisation in IELTS

Listening

Reading

Writing

Speaking

Modes of delivery

Test on paper

- This is the main mode of delivery at the moment. Listening, Reading and Writing test answers are all hand-written on IELTS answer sheets

Test on computer

- Answers to Listening, Reading and Writing tests are all typed directly onto the computer
- The Speaking Test is the same for both tests on paper and tests on computer: face-to-face, one-to-one with a trained examiner

IELTS Online

- Allows test takers to take IELTS anywhere, provided they have a stable internet connection and quiet, private space.
- Only available in selected countries.

Modes of delivery

Key points

- There is no difference in the content of the tests
- There is no difference in the value of the results e.g., a 6.5 is the same whether the test was taken on paper, on computer or online
- Test takers will be able to choose which mode of delivery they want to have

Integration of Video Call Speaking

**Introducing
Video-Call
Speaking Test**

Same experience.
Same examiners.
Same test.

The IELTS on Computer test: Peculiarities and Advantages

Which number do you hear?

The Listening Test

1. Daniel lives at **13 / 30** Bridgewater Road.
2. Laura was **14 / 40** when she learned to swim.
3. The doctor's clinic is at **15 / 50** Manor Street.
4. The student scored **16 / 60** marks in his test.
5. We used to live in an apartment building with **17 / 70** other people.
6. Susan has **19 / 90** books in her office.

The Academic Reading test

Reading task types - matching headings and summary completion

Attend this week's **live IELTS webinar** to have the chance to use skim reading skills in longer texts. You'll also get to practise a strategy for matching headings and to learn an approach to the summary completion task.

The Academic Writing test

WRITING

TIPS

Do make an effort to clearly understand the IELTS Writing criteria:

- Task Achievement/Response
- Coherence and Cohesion
- Lexical Resource
- Grammatical Range and Accuracy

I trust the test
that helps me
*achieve
my best*

New

IELTS One Skill Retake

from BRITISH COUNCIL

IELTS Preparation Support

Visit IELTS website [takeielts.org](https://www.takeielts.org) for various support materials including free practice tests

[Free IELTS preparation webinars and IELTS Study Pack](#)

Sign up and get access to our free weekly IELTS webinars and our brand new IELTS Study Pack!

[Free online IELTS practice tests](#)

Prepare for IELTS with our free practice tests and answers.

[IELTS Progress Check](#)

IELTS Progress Check is an official, online practice test. Completed tests are marked by IELTS trained and qualified markers and you will receive a Feedback Report including an indicative band score for each section of the test.

[IELTS for UKVI and Life Skills practice tests](#)

Prepare for your IELTS for UK Visas and Immigration (Academic) on computer test with free sample questions.

[Free IELTS mobile apps](#)

Our free IELTS apps allow you to learn English flexibly – wherever you are and whenever you want to prepare.

[IELTS expert Facebook sessions](#)

The IELTS Expert Live Sessions on Facebook give test takers the opportunity to interact with an IELTS teacher and ask questions about the test.

[IELTS on computer preparation](#)

Use our range of practice materials to familiarise yourself with the IELTS on computer test and improve your English level.

[IELTS preparation courses](#)

Prepare for your IELTS test with a range of IELTS study materials and resources from the British Council.

[IELTS Coach – personalised, online coaching](#)

Join our fully personalised online IELTS preparation course with IELTS experts. Combine online group or private live classes to maximise your score.

[IELTS books and study guides](#)

You can benefit from a wide range of IELTS preparation books and materials, created by some of the world's leading English language specialists.

IELTS Ready

Member vs Premium

Through IELTS Ready the British Council provides an unparalleled level of IELTS preparation support, both before and after registration for a test. For the highest level of preparation support test takers need to register to access the IELTS Ready Premium platform. Below are the key features of each level.

TakeIELTS

Free access to general information and basic preparation support

- Access to Free IELTS (one AC and GT) practice test, IELTS for UKVI practice test
- Information on Test format, Free webinars and Facebook Live sessions, IELTS Prep App, and IELTS books and study guides
- Information on IELTS Progress Check, EnglishScore Tutors, IELTS Coach, Teaching centre Preparation courses (Paid services)

IELTS Ready Member

Free access to the Member provides valuable information on how to excel in the test upon basic account creation.

Key features include:

- Free online access to 6 mock tests and speaking practice
- Practice exercises for all question types
- Tips and videos for score improvement
- Free IELTS preparation webinars
- 8 videos for new test takers and 4 for repeat test takers

IELTS Ready Premium

Complimentary access to the Premium section on purchasing IELTS with British Council. Key features include:

- Personalised study plan
- 40 full practice tests
- 25 Academic and 15 General exams available, all 4 sections
- Live and recorded lessons.
- Adaptive practice questions tailored to test takers' abilities
- Comprehensive guidance and model answers to enhance test takers' performance in reading, writing, and listening sections.
- Mobile Friendly

Thank you

IELTS